

ARTWIN

INDUSTRY & CONSTRUCTION
4.0 SOLUTIONS

Dissemination, Awareness raising and Communication Plan – Final

Version

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Executive Summary

This document constitutes the updated and final version of the Dissemination, Awareness raising and Communication Plan (DACP) of the ARTwin project.

ARTwin is a Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Action aiming to develop and introduce an easily deployable platform that enables the design and maintenance of highly accurate digital representations of real environments, be they factories or construction sites (Digital Twin or BIM), that are updated in real time and allow for the deployment of high-quality interactive services, well-tailored to the requirements of Industry and Construction 4.0.

This final version of the Dissemination, Awareness raising and Communication Plan builds on the initial strategy developed in D6.1 and focuses on both the evaluation of the activities implemented during the first half of the project and the dissemination targets for the next period, outlining specific actions and activities expected by the ARTwin consortium members, to ensure communication success and maximum publicity of the project's results, taking into account possible consequences of the COVID-19 crisis. It elaborates on:

- the objectives of the dissemination strategy, as well as the defined framework (the communication tools/instruments to reach out to the target groups, the time plan for disseminating the project's results, the consortium responsibilities and the relevant work packages and milestones);
- any adaptations needed to the initial Dissemination, Awareness raising and Communication Plan, following from the experience of the 1st half of the project's implementation and the COVID-19 crisis.

This deliverable corresponds to the Task 6.1 "Dissemination and communication strategy, plan and activities" of Work Package (WP) 6 "Dissemination, communication and exploitation".

Table of Contents

1.	INTRODUCTION	3
2.	DISSEMINATION ASSETS	4
3.	TARGET GROUPS	5
3.1	Graphical identity and promotional material	7
3.1.1	<i>Logo.....</i>	7
3.1.2	<i>Leaflets and posters</i>	8
3.1.3	<i>Templates.....</i>	8
3.1.4	<i>Videos.....</i>	8
3.2	ARTwin’s web portal and partners’ web portals	8
3.3	Social media networks	11
3.4	Online newsletter and mailing list	12
3.5	Publications.....	14
3.5.1	<i>Open access to scientific publication and relevant repositories.....</i>	14
3.6	Participation in external events	15
3.7	ARTwin workshops	17
3.8	ARTwin Final Conference.....	18
3.9	Synergies with relevant initiatives and Standardisation Bodies	18
3.10	EU dissemination channels	19
4.	PUBLICITY TIMETABLE	20
5.	CONCLUSIONS	21

List of figures

Figure 1. Dissemination, awareness raising and communication activities	6
Figure 2. ARTwin’s logo.....	7
Figure 3. ARTwin deliverables’ templates	8
Figure 4. “Our first demos” section on the landing page of the ARTwin website.	9
Figure 5. “Key aspects simply explained” section on the landing page of the ARTwin website.	10
Figure 6. AR marker based experience on the landing page of ARTwin’s website (1/2). ..	10
Figure 7. AR marker based experience on the landing page of ARTwin’s website (1/2). ..	11

List of tables

Table 1. ARTwin’s main exploitable assets	4
Table 2. ARTwin’s main target groups	5
Table 3. ARTwin’s social media accounts	12
Table 4. Action plan for the dissemination, awareness raising and communication activities	20

1. Introduction

This report, titled “**D6.5: Dissemination, Awareness raising and Communication Plan – Final version**”, constitutes the second version of the DACP, introducing the updated dissemination and communication strategy, along with the associated actions that will continue to be implemented throughout the next months of the project. With that in mind, this deliverable outlines the approach to (i) effectively communicate the project and disseminate its results, (ii) guide the partners in planning and implementing their individual dissemination activities and (iii) continuously monitor the efficiency and the timely planning of the actions.

With the updated plans and actions described, the ARTwin consortium aims to meet the following dissemination objectives:

- To effectively promote the project and its outcomes to all possible target groups / audiences in national and European level;
- Establish and maintain procedures for timely and effective communication with all targeted groups as well as coordinate all levels and types of communication and interaction in relation to the project;
- Foster the development of the ARTwin platform brand and image;
- Encourage interactions amongst stakeholders and establish synergies with other relevant projects and initiatives.

With the above in mind, the “Dissemination, Awareness raising and Communication Plan – Final version” is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 1 - Introduction:** Provides introductory information with respect to the DACP and its structure.
- **Chapter 2 - Dissemination assets:** Presents the main project’s assets to be disseminated throughout the period of the grant and beyond.
- **Chapter 3 - Target groups:** Presents the key stakeholder groups that will serve as the main audiences for the project’s dissemination, awareness raising and communication campaign.
- **Chapter 4 - Channels and tools:** Encompasses all the channels and tools that will be utilized for the dissemination activities of the project.
- **Chapter 5 - Time plan:** Provides the timeframe for the communication, awareness raising and dissemination activities of the project partners.
- **Chapter 6 - Performance indicators and monitoring:** Identifies the indicators to measure success on the dissemination actions, enabling partners to refine efforts over the course of the project.
- **Chapter 7 - Conclusions:** Pertains to the conclusions of the updated Dissemination, Awareness raising and Communication Plan, as well as the way forward.

2. Dissemination assets

The assets that follow will be disseminated by all partners with a view to maximizing the project’s impact and visibility. This information will be conveyed in a meaningful way and well-tailored to each stakeholder group (to be described further below).

- **Vision and aim** - The vision, aim and strategic objectives of the project will be widely disseminated along with all the conceptual aspects of the project, namely the whole project concept, its innovative characteristics, its impact both in industry and construction, etc.
- **News** – News pertaining to the technical achievements of the project, like the Artwin platform and its services, will be highly communicated once these tools are developed.
- **Events** - The events organised by the project, namely the two workshops focusing on end-users and the Final Conference will be widely disseminated to attract stakeholders from the project’s target groups, along with the events that the partners participate in (e.g. to present scientific papers).
- **Scientific knowledge** - The scientific knowledge that derives from the project, in the form of public deliverables and scientific publications, will be promoted in journals with high impact factor, in major scientific and industrial events, as well as through widely used online platforms and repositories.
- **Main exploitable assets** - Key project’s assets, as depicted in Table 1, will be disseminated as widely as possible in order to stimulate the interest of prospective end-customers and nurture the ground for their post-project rollout.

Table 1. ARTwin’s main exploitable assets

ARTwin’s main assets
The ARTwin platform integrating the project’s interactive technologies providing the following services:
- Development and updating of a unified global map of the factory/construction site
- Localisation service to track AR devices
- Development and real-time updating of a 3D Digital Twin/BIM of a factory/construction site
- AR Remote Rendering service for displaying complex 3D models on low resources AR devices
- ARTwin Business Model(s) and Plan(s)
-Research data and scientific publications stemming from the research, development and pilot demonstration and evaluation activities, offering meaningful utility to stakeholders from the research and academic community
-The ARTwin brand and community created and enhanced throughout the duration of the project, facilitating the dissemination and commercial exploitation of the project’s assets
-Public project reports / deliverables

These dissemination assets are still valid for the 2nd half of the ARTwin project and thus no revision is necessary.

3. Target groups

The key stakeholders of ARTwin can be segmented in the target groups outlined in table 2 below.

Table 2. ARTwin's main target groups

ARTwin's target stakeholder groups	
Industrial stakeholders (Industry 4.0/ Construction)	Businesses that may serve as end-users of the ARTwin platform and their personnel
	- Workers in industrial and construction environments
	- Managers tasked with the design of work flows as well as with operations / resource planning (e.g. shop floor/technical managers and planners, etc.)
	- Decision-makers in leading industrial businesses that have the potential to adopt the solutions of ARTwin (such CEOs, VPs, high-level HR executives, etc.)
	Businesses who may develop their own applications based on the ARTwin platform, or businesses that may serve as partners / collaborators (e.g. technology and software providers, equipment manufacturers, etc.)
	Industry-driven networks and associations (such as European Factories of the Future Research Association (EFFRA) etc.)
Academic and research stakeholders	Influencers within worker-led communities, networks and associations that can advocate the benefits of ARTwin
	Academics, researchers and experts focused on advancing the scientific fields cross-cutting ARTwin (e.g. VR, AR, Artificial Intelligence, Workplace Innovation, User-centred Innovation, Computer Vision, Cloud Technology, etc.)
Governmental/ policy stakeholders and Standardisation Bodies	Related EU-funded projects and initiatives
	European Technology Platforms (such as Manufuture, ECTP, NESSI, EPoSS, etc.)
	National and EU regulators and policy-makers in relevant public authorities (such as industrial committees, ministries and regional councils, etc.)
	EU Institutions and Agencies (e.g. the EC, European Science Foundation, MEPs)
Other stakeholders	Standardisation bodies (e.g. ETSI, Word Wide Web Consortium, ISO/IEC, Khronos Group, etc.)
	General public

The identified target groups are still valid for the 2nd half of the ARTwin project and thus no revision is necessary.

Channels and tools

Several dissemination channels and tools of the ARTwin project will be utilized for awareness raising and stakeholder engagement throughout the duration of the project and beyond. These channels and tools are presented in the following list:

1. Graphical identity and promotional material
2. Project's web-portal and partners' web-portals
3. Project's social media accounts (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube) and partners' social media accounts
4. Online newsletters
5. Publications
6. Participation in external events
7. ARTwin workshops
8. ARTwin Final Conference
9. Synergies with relevant initiatives and Standardisation Bodies
10. EU dissemination channels

The assets of the project will be distributed through the aforementioned channels and tools to all targeted groups. This process will involve all the activities depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Dissemination, awareness raising and communication activities

All partners will actively participate and contribute to the dissemination and stakeholder engagement efforts both at organization as well as individual level.

3.1 Graphical identity and promotional material

The creation of a graphical identity and promotional material is key for enabling the effective dissemination of the project and its activities. Promotional material will be used both at project workshops and external events, where ARTwin partners participate. Also, it will be used in the everyday publicity of the project.

In compliance with the EU requirements on dissemination of results, as set in Grant Agreement number 856994, Article 29, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic), must display the EU emblem with appropriate prominence and also include the following text: *“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 856994”*. In applications for protecting results (including patent applications), the following text must be included: *“The project leading to this application has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 856994”*.

In reports and deliverables of public dissemination level, the following disclaimer must also be included: *“The current report reflects only the author’s view and the ARTwin Consortium and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains”*. All obligations, requirements and consequences of no-compliance stated in the Grant Agreement can be found in Annex I.

With that in mind, the main promotional material of the ARTwin project is described in the following sub-sections. Each partner will be responsible for translations (if considered necessary) and printing of the material according to its specific needs. **Partners should not produce any kind of promotional material, related to the project, without the previous review and approval of WP6 leader, Q-PLAN.**

3.1.1 Logo

ARTwin’s logo was developed in the beginning of the project (M1) and has been approved by all partners.

Figure 2. ARTwin’s logo

3.1.2 Leaflets and posters

A project leaflet and a poster presenting general information on the project (aim, objectives, partners, etc.) was created by M4 of the project. Apart from the general project leaflet and posters, specific printable promotional material for the promotion of ARTwin events and use cases schemes (e.g. fact sheets, etc.) will be prepared during the project, according to the needs of the partners.

3.1.3 Templates

Templates have been created for the consortium partners to be able to produce their project deliverables and their presentations. A template for the project's deliverables (both internal and public) as well as a template for the partners' presentations have been created and made available to project partners.

Figure 3. ARTwin deliverables' templates

3.1.4 Videos

A short video presenting ARTwin project will be produced so as to create awareness and efficiently boost the dissemination activities. The video will emphasize on promoting the project's results along with their value propositions as well as our demonstration activities. The preparation of the video is the responsibility of Q-PLAN. The video will be uploaded onto the YouTube channel of the project, that will be created later in the project and well before the publication of the video.

Apart from the promotional video, 3 more videos will be produced showcasing the usefulness of the ARTwin platform in the context of the project's 3 pilot use cases:

1. A video demonstrating the "AR enabled factory worker" use case in a Siemens factory
2. A video demonstrating the "Dynamic production line planning" use case in a Siemens factory
3. A video demonstrating the "Better constructions with AR" use case in the Eiffage Bretagne construction in Dinard, France

3.2 ARTwin's web portal and partners' web portals

The project's web portal was developed by M4 of the project (January 2020) and constitutes the main gateway to ARTwin's activities, deliverables, news and events. The web portal contains information about the project's concept and objectives, the ARTwin platform along with its services, the consortium and the

Advisory Board, the three use cases of the project, the most recent and active related projects, as well as project's news. Links to social media accounts of the project and to project partners' webpages are also included. As the project evolves, the web portal is being further enriched with all publishable deliverables and published scientific papers.

The news section of the ARTwin's web-portal is updated according to the availability of news and the web-portal is also equipped with an online subscription tool for visitors in order to subscribe to the project's newsletter. ARTwin's web portal will be available for at least five years after the period of the grant.

Q-PLAN is responsible for the design, operation and update of the project's web-portal. All partners are required to create links to the project web-portal on their websites and to contribute with the news to be uploaded, as well as to publish occasionally news of the project to the web-portals of their organizations. The ARTwin's portal will be mentioned in all publicity material generated by the project Consortium.

Following the recommendations provided by the external reviewers of ARTwin during its Interim Review Meeting (September 18th 2020), the ARTwin website has been updated to become more dynamic and interactive.

In particular, the recommendation was:

Recommendation #8: The ARTwin web portal appears to be quite static for a project dealing with interactive technology such as AR. It is recommended to **include some videos that are already available and were shown during the review meeting** and interactivity with the prospective target audiences in the form of AR experiences to the user (**marker based on the screen**), **possibly in conjunction with free apps available on most operating systems**. It is highly recommended that the consortium **updates the information on the web portal to be more dynamic and interactive** in order to maximise the impact on the target audiences (e.g. the **inclusion of videos of results, promotional videos, AR marker based experiences embedded within the web pages**, etc.) (Recommendation #8).

And the actions that were taken to address it were:

1. Creation of a new section on the landing page of the ARTwin website to present the first demos developed by partners. This section includes the video demos that were presented during the Interim Review Meeting.

Figure 4. "Our first demos" section on the landing page of the ARTwin website.

2. Development of an additional section on the landing page to display with a video the key technical aspects of the project. The video that was used for this section is the recording of the dedicated webinar that was organised by the Augmented Reality for Enterprise Alliance – AREA to present the ARTwin project.

Key aspects simply explained

The ARTwin project was presented on October 21st 2020 in a dedicated webinar hosted by the Augmented Reality for Enterprise Alliance – AREA!!

By watching this video you will have the opportunity to learn about (i) the three use cases on which the ARTwin project research focuses, (ii) the approaches to mapping, modelling and maintaining digital representations of target spaces, (iii) the architecture of the testbed/system, (iv) how 3D AR localization is performed and finally (v) the current status and challenges.

Figure 5. “Key aspects simply explained” section on the landing page of the ARTwin website.

3. Development of an AR marker-based experience on the landing page of ARTwin’s website, to show through a short video the key concepts of ARTwin. The application that is used for the scanning of the marker is the free app ARloopa <https://app.arloopa.com/>

Artwin in a nutshell

Scan the image to find out in less than 2 mins what Artwin is all about!

Download the app here: <https://app.arloopa.com/>

Use cases

Figure 6. AR marker based experience on the landing page of ARTwin’s website (1/2).

Figure 7. AR marker based experience on the landing page of ARTwin's website (1/2).

Additional activities foreseen in the 2nd period, include the development and uploading of 4 new videos, that are presented in section 4.1.4 of the current document.

Apart from the above, in light with the performance monitored in the first 18 months, and taking into account the target for the number of visits to the ARTwin web portal, we can conclude that efforts need to be made in the next period to:

- Increase the traffic to the website
- Increase the traffic through organic search and through referral and raise the number of external links to the website.

To achieve this, we will need to work during the next period on two key fronts:

- Content: There is a need to improve the content available on the website. More particularly, publishing news relevant to the project on the website and parallel promoting through the social media will offer incentives to visitors to visit the website.
- Generating more back links to the website to generate more traffic through referrals.

3.3 Social media networks

The creation of a Facebook page, a LinkedIn page, a Twitter account and a YouTube channel is considered as a key to the communication of the project's news, events and outcomes. To this end, all social media accounts have been created in M2 of the project (November 2019), except from the YouTube channel which will be created later in the project.

Table 3. ARTwin's social media accounts

Social Media Platform	ARTwin's URL
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/ARTwin-Project-110545737082313/
Twitter	https://twitter.com/ArtwinProject
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/artwin-project/about/

The project's social media are continuously updated in English with news about the project's activities and results, various events, scientific news, news from several organizations / associations that promote the integration of interactive technologies in industry and construction, news from related EU projects, etc.

A YouTube channel will be created later in the project, when the promotional videos of the final demonstrators will be developed and made available online. Besides the videos demonstrating the ARTwin's 3 use cases, a promotional video will be uploaded on the project's YouTube channel and emphasize on promoting the project's results along with their value propositions.

Q-PLAN is responsible for the administration of the ARTwin's social media accounts. All partners are required to become members or/and followers of the social media accounts, to actively like the social media posts of the project, to disseminate our posts through their personal networks, as well as to publish posts and news about ARTwin regularly, through the social media of their organizations.

As of March 2021, the social media followers count up to 763 people. The social media channels are set to grow however additional efforts are required from the project partners in order to attract more followers and reach the KPI (>2000 followers) set in the DoA Part B.

The role of project partners in this respect is outlined by the following table.

Task/Campaign	Activity	Partner(s)	Status
Social Media Channels	Set up & maintain ARTwin social media pages	Q-PLAN	Done (YouTube pending)
	Provide Q-PLAN with messages to be published on social media	All partners	Monthly
	Post content on social media pages	Q-PLAN	Monthly
	Connect with relevant contacts	Q-PLAN	Continuous
	Monitor metrics	Q-PLAN	Every 3 months

3.4 Online newsletter and mailing list

Online newsletters are prepared and distributed through MailChimp, presenting among others the achieved results, upcoming activities and events, news from similar initiatives and news in the relevant scientific fields. The frequency of newsletter issues depends on the amount and importance of news to be presented, with

the target to produce a newsletter at least every 6 months, however additional ad-hoc newsletters may be added if deemed necessary.

The newsletter recipients' list is continuously updated during the project, as everyone who is interested is able to subscribe to the recipients' list by registering on the newsletter section of the project's website. The recipients' list may also be used for the dissemination of other news and announcements related to the project activities.

The newsletter issues are prepared by Q-PLAN, with the contribution of all partners regarding the content. The content of each issue is decided and agreed among the consortium. Partners are also required to disseminate the newsletter issues through their own dissemination channels.

All partners will contribute to the content and will reuse selected content from the ARTwin newsletters in their own newsletters. Statistics and results on the newsletters will be monitored via the MailChimp account for the ARTwin newsletter and from information provided by the partners for their own newsletters. With that in mind, the role of project partners in this framework is presented with further detail by the table which follows.

Task/Campaign	Activity	Partner(s)	Status
Newsletter	Set up structure and design look for ARTwin newsletter	Q-PLAN	Done
	Collect content for newsletter	Q-PLAN	Every 6 months, for each Newsletter
	Provide content for newsletter	All partners	Every 6 months, for each Newsletter
	Check for ad-hoc newsletter need	Q-PLAN	Ad-hoc
	Collect content for ad-hoc newsletter	Q-PLAN	Ad-hoc
	Provide content for ad-hoc newsletters	All partners	Ad-hoc
	Prepare and send out newsletters to subscribed stakeholders	Q-PLAN	Every 6 months and ad-hoc
	Integrate form on the website to allow stakeholders sign-up	Q-PLAN	Done

	Monitor newsletters statistics	Q-PLAN	Every 6 months for regular newsletter, Ad-hoc after each ad-hoc newsletter
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3.5 Publications

Both scientific (articles in scientific journals / conferences) and non-scientific (press releases, blogs, etc.) publications will be produced during the project by all project partners. Scientific knowledge generated during the project is shared in scientific conferences and open access journals. All partners are responsible for identifying any publishing opportunities and for carrying out all necessary actions to ensure publications of project results. All partners do not have the same capacity regarding publications, therefore each partner will undertake the kind of publication (scientific or non-scientific) that is deemed as more suitable. Each partner will make effort to produce publications in the highest quality, which not only reflects on the consortiums' reputation but also on the ARTwin initiative. All publications must cite or/and refer to the EU contribution and project grant agreement number, as required in the Article 29 of the Grant Agreement no 856994.

3.5.1 *Open access to scientific publication and relevant repositories*

All peer reviewed publications will be deposited either with green open access (i.e. the author, or a representative, archives the published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript in an online repository before, at the same time as, or after publication), or with gold open access (an article is immediately published in open access mode and the payment of publication costs is shifted away from subscribing readers), according to the [“Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020”](#).

The ARTwin consortium will ensure visibility of the public knowledge lying in public deliverables, open data and scientific publications by sharing them on other widely used platforms and repositories (e.g. Zenodo, OpenAIR, etc.), besides the project's website and social media.

During the Interim Review Meeting a recommendation was made by the external reviewers to increase the number of scientific publications stemming directly from ARTwin's research activities:

In particular, the recommendation was:

Recommendation #5: It is highly recommended to **intensify the dissemination and communication activities** in the next period as per DoA. As it is planned in the DoA, an exploitable asset will be the scientific publications stemming from the research, development and pilot demonstration and evaluation activities, offering meaningful utility to stakeholders from the research and academic community. It is therefore **expected that more scientific publications will be produced** when results from ARTwin developments are matured. There were several research publications presented from the outset. However, the consortium should **make sure that the presented research work directly comes from the project research activities and include all necessary disclaimer and acknowledgments** (Recommendation #10).

In line with this recommendation, over the course of the 2nd period of the project, consortium partners are planning to produce several scientific papers emerging directly from the research, development, pilot

demonstration and evaluation activities of ARTwin, which will be offered to the research community in open access.

Each partner is responsible for identifying any publishing opportunities and for carrying out all necessary actions to ensure publications of project results. Q-PLAN, to support the partners' efforts in this direction, has made a list of Conferences in the fields cross-cutting ARTwin, whereby scientific papers could be published (see paragraph 3.6 below).

3.6 Participation in external events

The partners of the ARTwin consortium will participate in several external events (at least 30) with the aim to boost the dissemination of project's activities and results. The targeted events, both scientific and business, will relate to the knowledge fields of the project, the sectors it covers as well as the interests of the project's primary stakeholders. The goal is to keep in touch with the latest advances in the research and industry across Europe, share knowledge with respective communities, and establish contacts and interactions with key stakeholders, while at the same time communicating the results of the project. Partners participating in external events (exhibitions, business events, information days, scientific events and conferences) should disseminate the ARTwin project following the guidelines below:

- Before the event, it is necessary to complete "ARTwin_future_events.xls" with the required information about the event.
- If a partner is making a presentation, it is requested to use the ARTwin presentation template.
- During the event, it is important to disseminate the project's promotional material (leaflets, etc.).
- A number of photos must be taken.
- The partner is requested to update the Dissemination and Communication Manager about the participation in the event and to share the photos taken, not later than ten days after the event.
- All partners are asked to complete the third sheet of the "ARTwin_dissemination_activities.xls", named "External Events" with all required information about the participation in the event at the latest three weeks after the event.

Due to COVID-19 and traveling restrictions, participation in events and conferences by consortium partners has been significantly reduced. As a mitigation measure, project partners will mostly attend events that are organized remotely, at least until normality is restored.

In parallel, following the external reviewers comments to intensify dissemination efforts, a list with suitable external conferences and events has been created for the 1st semester of 2021, and will be updated regularly for the semesters to come, in order to facilitate partners in identifying opportunities for attending an interesting event and/or presenting their scientific papers.

Title	Date	Place	URL
International Conference on Computer Engineering and Digital Representation	January 18-19, 2021	Online	

International Conference on Mixed Reality Technologies	January 21-22, 2021	Online	
International Conference on Advances in Augmented Reality Technologies	January 28-29, 2021	Online	
Automation, Robotics & Communications for Industry 4.0: 1st IFSA Winter Conference	Feb 3, 2021 - Feb 5, 2021	Chamonix-Mount-Blanc, France	
Accelerating Digital Transformation in a Post-COVID World	February 8-11, 2021	Online	
International Conference on Frontiers in Information and Communication Technologies	February 11-12, 2021	Online	
International Conference on Augmented Reality Technologies	February 15-16, 2021	Online	
International Conference on Augmented Reality Technologies and Applications	February 15-16, 2021	Online	
International Conference on Mixed Reality	February 18-19, 2021	Online	
International Conference on Advances in Augmented Reality	March 11-12, 2021	Online	
International Conference on Augmented Reality Technology	March 15-16, 2021	Online	
International Conference on Recent Advances in Augmented Reality Technologies	March 22-23, 2021	Online	
International Conference on Augmented Reality and Design Process	March 29-30, 2021	Online	
International Conference on Mixed Reality Technology	April 08-09, 2021	Online	
International Conference on Advances in Computer Science, Machine Learning and Big Data	April 12-13, 2021	Online	

International Conference on Computer Science, Machine Learning and Big Data	April 2021	12-13,	Online	
International Conference on Recent Advances in Mixed Reality Technologies and Applications	April 2021	12-13,	Online	
International Conference on Advances in Mixed Reality Technologies	April 2021	15-16,	Online	
LAVAL VIRTUAL 2021	14-16 2021	April,	France	
ETSI IoT week	26-30 2021	April	TBC	
International Conference on Advances in Mixed Reality Technologies and Applications	May 2021	03-04,	Online	
International Conference on Recent Advances in Mixed Reality Technologies	May 2021	13-14,	Online	
International Conference on Recent Advances in Augmented Reality	May 2021	24-25,	Online	
International Conference on Recent Advances in Computer Science, Machine Learning and Big Data	June 2021	03-04,	Online	
European Conference on Networks and Communications	June 2021	8-11,	Porto, Portugal	
Double Conference: World Class Connected Industry + Digital Twins 2021	June 2021	24-25,	Frankfurt Germany	
International Conference on Industrial Digitalization and the Internet of Things	July 2021	15-16,	Online	

3.7 ARTwin workshops

During the project, two workshops will take place dedicated to familiarizing end-users with the ARTwin platform. The workshops will be organised along with the pilots, by SIE and ART respectively, and they will include demo sessions so as to showcase the project's benefits, gather end-user feedback for further improvements, as well as investigate the interest for the commercial exploitation of the ARTwin solution. Local dissemination campaigns for the workshops will be under the responsibility of the organizer partner, with the support of Q-PLAN for central level dissemination (project web-portal and social media, newsletter

and massive e-mail sender tool for dispatch of invitations, press release in English, and promotional material in English). All activities implemented under those workshops as well as their results will be reported in the “Results of dissemination and communication activities” (deliverable D6.7).

Planning for the ARTwin workshops is still valid and does not need to be updated. In the case that restrictions due to COVID-19 are still in force at the time of the workshops, suitable mitigation measures will be taken beforehand.

3.8 ARTwin Final Conference

By the end of the project, a Final Conference will take place, organized by all project partners under the lead of Q-PLAN and it will probably be organized as satellite at a larger international event. The aim of the conference will be to spread the accumulated knowledge and present the final achievements to scientists, industry, policy makers and generally to all interested parties, with a view to fostering industrial and research utilisation of the project results, as well as contribution to standards. ARTwin’s partners should contribute to further disseminate the final event through their personal networks. All activities implemented towards the organization of this conference will be reported in the second version of the “Results of dissemination and communication activities” (deliverable D6.7).

Planning for the ARTwin Final Conference is still valid and does not need to be updated. In the case that restrictions due to COVID-19 are still in force, suitable mitigation measures will be taken beforehand.

3.9 Synergies with relevant initiatives and Standardisation Bodies

Synergies with other relevant EU-funded or international initiatives are pursued by all partners in project’s research domains and industry sectors, to facilitate knowledge exchange, to gain mutual dissemination benefits and to exploit potential cooperation.

Possible synergies may comprise of participation in events of similar projects, dissemination of ARTwin’s promotional material in events of similar projects, invitations to participate in ARTwin’s events, exchange of news through each project’s channels, inclusion of the project’s web-portal and social media as links in websites and social media of other projects, provision of feedback in each project’s activities, etc.

Project partners should keep track of all similar projects and initiatives which might be interested in collaboration and should regularly enrich the list. All partners should keep in mind that the ARTwin dissemination strategy cannot reach its full potential unless meaningful collaboration with related projects is established.

In particular, partners’ roles in this respect are as shown in the table below.

Task/Campaign	Activity	Partner(s)	Status
Collaboration with other projects	Identify projects relevant to collaborate with and the potential type of collaboration	All partners	Ad-hoc (once a good opportunity identified)

	Discuss with relevant projects and identify the types of synergies	Q-PLAN (with the support of partners if needed)	Ad-hoc
	Establish collaboration and implement jointly agreed actions	Q-PLAN (with the support of partners if needed)	Ad-hoc
	Monitor outreach	Q-PLAN	Quarterly

Alongside, ARTwin partners, and mainly BCM and SIE, will seek to actively contribute to the activity Standardisation Bodies, with a view to fostering a growing and sustainable AR ecosystem across Europe, all while enhancing the brand of the ARTwin project and its solutions.

3.10 EU dissemination channels

The following EU dissemination channels could be used during the project:

- **Open Research Europe.** EC is offering through Open Research Europe fast publication along with peer review and open access at no cost for research stemming from Horizon 2020 funding across all subject areas.
- **OpenAIRE portal.** OpenAIRE provides “an electronic infrastructure and supporting mechanisms for the identification, deposition, access, and monitoring of FP7 and ERC funded articles”.
- **EIT Digital and EIT Manufacturing.** EIT Digital and EIT Manufacturing support the development of dynamic pan-European partnerships among leading companies, research and academia dedicated to finding solutions for digitalization and efficient manufacturing across Europe respectively.
- **European Cooperation in Science and Technology.** The cooperation connects research initiatives across Europe and enables researchers and innovators to grow their ideas in technology by sharing them with peers.
- **CORDIS (Community Research and Development Information Service) WIRE.** CORDIS WIRE is a CORDIS online service that helps research and business community to promote projects’ activities by publishing news and events on CORDIS.
- **EU industry days and info-days, workshops and conferences.** Events organised by DG CONECT focusing on AR/ VR (e.g. interactive technologies workshops, etc.)

The Project Officer will be contacted with regards to possible dissemination steps supported by the EU.

4. Publicity timetable

Table 4. Action plan for the dissemination, awareness raising and communication activities

Activity	Partner	WP	2021					2022				
			April - May	June- July	Aug. – Sep.	Oct.- Nov.	Dec.-Jan.	Feb. – Mar.	Apr. - May	June- July	Aug. – Sep.	
Videos	Q-PLAN	WP6										
Publicity through web portal	All partners	All WPs										
Publicity through partners' web portals	All partners	All WPs										
Publicity through projects' social media	All partners	All WPs										
Publicity through partners' social media	All partners	All WPs										
Creation and publicity through YouTube channel	Q-PLAN	WP6										
Mailing list formation	Q-PLAN	WP6										
E - newsletter	Q-PLAN	WP6										
Non – scientific publications	All partners	WP2- WP6										
Scientific publications	All partners	WP2- WP5										
Exhibitions, business events, information days etc.	All partners	WP6										
Scientific events, conferences etc.	All partners	WP6										
1 st Workshop	Q-PLAN, SIE	WP5										
2 nd Workshop	Q-PLAN, ART	WP5										
ARtwin Final Conference	All partners	All WPs										
Establishment of synergies with relevant initiatives	Q-PLAN, All	WP6										
EIT Digital, EIT Manufacturing, CORDIS, OpenAIRE	Q-PLAN	WP6										

Beyond the end of the project, partners are committed to continue disseminating the project's outcomes through their everyday activities, networks and means of communication employed to reach related stakeholder groups. The stakeholders that will have participated in the activities of the project are expected to act as multipliers of the ARTwin's results beyond its lifespan.

5. Conclusions

The current document constitutes the second version of the Dissemination, Awareness Raising and Communication Plan of the ARtwin project. It has been developed by Q-PLAN under the Task 6.1 “Dissemination and communication strategy, plan and activities” of Work Package 6 “Dissemination, communication and exploitation”.

With reference to the initial plan elaborated in D6.1, this report describes the objectives and the defined framework of ARtwin project’s dissemination strategy and provides an update of the planned dissemination activities and foreseen channels, following the experience of the 1st half of the project’s implementation.

To conclude, all partners should keep on actively contributing to the dissemination activities through the exploitation of the defined dissemination tools and channels, promoting and multiplying publicity of the project’s aims and achievements and disseminating targeted messages to all relevant stakeholders. All the relevant activity of the consortium will be summarised in a final report that will be delivered by the end of the project, in September 2022 (M36).